

How do oxidoreduction conditions affect the balance of volatile compounds produced by lactic acid bacteria in a curd-based medium?

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Abstract

The oxidoreduction potential (E_h) of cheeses may affect the balance of volatile compounds that determine their flavour, but few studies are available on this topic. We explored the effect of E_h on the production of volatile compounds by lactic acid bacteria in cheese-like conditions. A strain of *Lactococcus lactis* subsp. *lactis* (Lc) and a strain of *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* (Lb) were inoculated individually in a curd-based medium, either in the presence of O₂ (O2), or in the presence of N₂ (N2), and incubated at 26°C until 26 days. Microbial numeration and volatile compounds composition were analysed each 7 days and E_h and pH were monitored all over the incubation. Lc was inoculated at 10⁷ ufc.mL⁻¹ and Lb at 10⁶ ufc.mL⁻¹. Numbers were higher in N2 samples for Lc all over the incubation and in O2 ones for Lb, except at 7 and 26 days. E_{h7} (E_h corrected with pH) kinetics differed between N2 and O2 samples with minima at -200 mV and -250 mV respectively after 7-32 h, values turning positive afterwards for Lc and remaining negative for Lb. pH remained constant all over the incubation. Forty-eight and fifty volatile compounds were extracted for Lc and Lb respectively. For Lc, 15 compounds were higher with O2 (8 aldehydes, 4 ketones, 2 oxidized sulphur compounds, 1 furan) and 3 with N2 (1 volatile acid, 2 alcohols); for Lb, 12 compounds were higher with O2 (4 aldehydes, 1 alcohol, 3 ketones, 2 oxidized sulphur compounds, 2 furans) and 3 with N2 (2 alcohols, 1 reduced sulphur compound). This study revealed a significant effect of O2/N2 on volatile compounds, similar for Lc and Lb despite different kinetics in microbial counts, E_h values and volatile compounds production.

Keywords: oxidoreduction, *Lactococcus*, *Lactiplantibacillus*, volatile compounds, curd-based medium

Introduction

The oxidoreduction potential (E_h) of cheeses may affect the balance of volatile compounds that determines their flavour, *via* an effect on the cheese microbiota. However, only few studies are available on this topic, in particular the effect of E_h on the production of volatile compounds by lactic acid bacteria (LAB). Addition of reducing or oxidizing agents was used by Kieronczyk *et al.* [1] with lactococci in a synthetic medium based on amino-acids, by Martin *et al.* [2] in non-fat yoghurt, by Caldeo *et al.* [3] in Cheddar. Ricciardi *et al.* [4] studied *Lactocaseibacillus casei* under anaerobic or respiratory conditions in whey permeate. We explored the effect of oxidoreduction conditions on the production of volatile compounds by two types of LAB *via* incubation in the presence of O₂ or N₂ in a medium and during a time that mimicked cheese during ripening.

Experimental

We inoculated individually a strain of *Lactococcus lactis* subsp. *lactis* (Lc) at 10⁷ ufc.mL⁻¹ and a strain of *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* (Lb) at 10⁶ ufc.mL⁻¹ in a curd-based medium made of 20h-semi-hard cheese curd ground in ultrapure water containing 18g.L⁻¹ NaCl, 1.2g.L⁻¹ peptone and lactose (1:2 w:w), sterilized 15 min at 110°C [5]. Two oxidoreduction conditions were applied for each strain: one inoculation in the presence of atmospheric O₂ (O2), the other one in an anaerobic chamber filled with N₂ (N2). For each strain and oxidoreduction condition, 70 mL of culture were distributed as follows: 3 mL in fifteen 10mL-SPME-vials, 1 mL in ten 10 mL-SPME-vials and 15 mL in one 40 mL-vial. Vials were incubated at 26°C until 26 days. Each 7 days, 1/5^o of SPME-vials were removed then analysed for microbial counts (one vial of 3 mL) and volatile compounds composition (two vials of 3 mL for neutral compounds and two vials of 1 mL for volatile fatty acids VFAs). Lc were numerated on M17 medium incubated 2 days at 20°C in aerobiosis and Lb on MRS medium incubated 3 days at 30°C in anaerobiosis. Neutral volatile compounds (or VFA) were analysed by SPME on CAR/PDMS 85µm (or 75 µm) fibre (Supelco, L'Isle d'Abeau, France) under agitation (or without agitation but with addition of H₂SO₄) at 40°C (or 60°C), 30 min (or 12 min) equilibration and 40 min (or 20 min) contact. GC/MS was performed with a 6890/5973 Agilent (Les Ulis, France), He at 73 kPa (or 43 kPa), a 60m/0.32mm/1µm RTX-5MS Restek (Lisses, France) column (or 30m/0.32 mm/0.5µm DB-Wax Agilent), 40°C-8 min (or 120°C-1 min) / 6°C.min⁻¹ until 145°C (or 180°C) / 20°C.min⁻¹ (or 10°C.min⁻¹) until 250°C (or 230°C). E_h and pH were monitored all over the incubation into vials of 15 mL with a combined electrode (InPro 3250i/SG/120, Mettler Toledo, Viroflay, France) and iCinac

software (AMS Alliance, Frépillon, France). E_{h7} was calculated to remove the effect of pH variations. The reduction rate $V_m = dE_{h7}.dt^{-1}$, T_m the time at which V_m occurred, and E_{h7m} the E_{h7} at which V_m occurred, were determined [6]. For each strain, the effect of time and O2/N2 on volatile compounds was studied by a 2-factor-ANOVA (XLSTAT software, Addinsoft, Paris, France). Compounds significantly affected at 5% were used to perform a principal component analysis (PCA), with a non-inoculated medium taken as reference.

Results and discussion

Microbial dynamics

Lc was inoculated at 10^7 ufc.mL⁻¹ and Lb at 10^6 ufc.mL⁻¹ (Figure 1). Numbers decreased all over the incubation period until 10^2 ufc.mL⁻¹ for Lc, but were at 10^6 ufc.mL⁻¹ at the end for Lb, after reaching a maximum of 10^7 ufc.mL⁻¹ between 7 (N2) and 14 (O2) days. Numbers were higher in N2 samples for Lc all over the incubation and in O2 ones for Lb, except at 7 and 26 days.

Figure 1: Counts of Lc (A) and Lb (B) in log (colony forming units.mL⁻¹) during the 26 days incubation in curd-based medium, according to O2 (in red) and N2 (in blue) conditions.

pH and oxidoreduction potential E_{h7}

The pH remained constant all over the incubation (Figure 2), which means that all lactose was exhausted in the curd at 20h. Despite a difference of inoculation level, kinetics of E_{h7} decrease were very similar between Lc and Lb (Figure 2). Brasca *et al.* [7] already observed similar minimal values of E_{h7} for *Lc. lactis* and *Lb. plantarum* inoculated in skimmed milk, but a faster decrease for the first. Conversely, E_{h7} kinetics differed between N2 and O2 samples, with minima at -200 mV and -250 mV after 7 and 32 h respectively. For Lc, with O2 and N2 respectively, V_m values were -358 and -260 mV/h, T_m values were 2.6 and 2.3 h, E_{h7m} values were 238 and 70 mV. For Lb with O2, V_m was -332 mV/h, T_m was 8.7 h, E_{h7m} was 63 mV, whereas with N2, values couldn't be calculated. Hence, Lc reached their maximum reduction rate before Lb (2.5 vs 8.7 h), in accordance with values of Brasca *et al.* [7], whereas Lc and Lb showed similar V_m and E_{h7m} values in similar O2 conditions. E_{h7} values became positive afterwards for Lc but remained negative for Lb. N2- E_{h7} values were lower than O2- E_{h7} values for Lc during most incubation, N2 values turning negative at the end. For Lb, the higher N2- E_{h7} than O2- E_{h7} values may result from a dysfunction of the N2 electrode, and so were the values of pH that may be similar to O2 values. This was consistent with the aberrant curve found for the calculation of kinetics parameters with the same electrode. This illustrates how the calibration of such electrodes is a difficult task [8].

Figure 2: pH (dotted lines) and E_{h7} (plain lines) kinetics for Lc (A) and Lb (B) during the 26 days incubation in curd-based medium, according to O2 (in red) and N2 (in blue) conditions.

Volatile compounds

For Lc (Lb), forty-eight (fifty) volatile compounds were extracted: 12(12) aldehydes, 11(11) ketones, 7(10) alcohols, 7(6) VFAs, 5(5) sulphur compounds, 4(4) esters, 2(2) furans. For Lc, only 2 ketones significantly decreased from 0 to 26 days, whereas 3 alcohols, 2 furans, one aldehyde, one VFA and one ester increased; for Lb, 5 aldehydes and 3 ketones decreased from 0 to 26 days, whereas 7 alcohols, 3 VFAs, 2 furans and one aldehyde increased. A similar evolution according to chemical classes of compounds has already been observed in cheeses [9]. It appears a large evolution from 0 to 7 days incubation, then a switch from 14 to 21 days for Lc and from 21 to 26 days for Lb (Figure 3). This switch was mainly related to alcohols increase and also VFAs for Lb and an ester for Lc. Concerning O₂/N₂ effect, for Lc, 3 compounds were significantly higher with N₂ (1 VFA, 2 alcohols) and 15 with O₂ (8 aldehydes, 4 ketones, 2 sulphur compounds in an oxidized form, 1 furan); for Lb, 3 compounds were higher with N₂ (2 alcohols, 1 sulphur compounds in a reduced form) and 12 with O₂ (4 aldehydes, 1 alcohol, 3 ketones, 2 sulphur compounds in an oxidized form, 2 furans).

Figure 3: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) made from volatile compounds significantly affected by inoculation time (*italics*) and O₂/N₂ (compounds increased by O₂ in red, by N₂ in blue) at 5% according to ANOVA. A: Lc, B: Lb. M=methyl, E=ethyl, P=penyl, C₄=butyric acid, C₆=caproic acid, iC₅=isovaleric acid, E-C₆=ethyl hexanoate, MSH=methanethiol, DMDS=dimethylsulphide, DMTS=dimethyltrisulphide, Benzald=Benzaldehyde, Bzacetald=Benzenacetald T0,7,14,21,26=incubation times of 0, 7, 14, 21, 26 days, Ref= medium without inoculation.

Despite different levels of incubation, different effects of O₂/N₂ on kinetics of counts and E_{h7} and different kinetics of volatile compounds production, very similar patterns of volatile compounds distribution according to O₂/N₂ were observed for Lc and for Lb. O₂ presence was favourable for many volatile compounds.

The metabolic way of production of diacetyl and acetoin from pyruvate is favoured by aerobiosis, and was already observed by Ricciardi *et al.* [4] with Lc in a whey permeate medium. Our results were also consistent with the oxidised / reduced form of compounds, the first being enhanced by aerobiosis, the second by anaerobiosis.

Aldehydes (butanal, pentanal, hexanal, heptanal, octanal, 2-methyl-propanal, 2-methyl-butanal, 3-methyl-butanal, benzaldehyde) and methyl-ketones (2-butanone, 2-hexanone, 2-octanone) are the oxidized form of corresponding alcohols (represented here by ethanol and 2-propanol). Similarly, dimethyldisulphide and dimethyltrisulphide, enhanced by O₂, are sulphur compounds in an oxidized form, whereas methanethiol, favoured by N₂, is a reduced sulphur compound. Lastly, furans may originate from the oxidation of fatty acids. Such a balance of aldehydes, ketones and alcohols was not observed by Ricciardi *et al.* [4]. This may be related to the time of incubation, only 48 h in their study, *i.e.* during the exponential and stationary phases of growth, whereas our incubation time reflected the period of cheese ripening. Kieronczyk *et al.* [1] observed a similar pattern than our results for aldehydes, sulphur compounds and acids for Lc in a synthetic amino acids-based medium, and Martin *et al.* [2] for sulphur compounds in yoghurt. Compared to these authors, the present study in a curd-based medium revealed an additional effect on alcohols, ketones and furans. Lastly, in 2-months Cheddar, Caldeo *et al.* [3] found the same trends for aldehydes, but the opposite for sulphur compounds, which emphasizes the importance of the studied medium.

In our study, a 20h-curd-based medium was chosen to mimic cheese conditions, *i.e.* the medium in which the secondary microbiota develops after the activity of starters, particularly lactose depletion. Moreover, a 26 days incubation may mimic the ripening phase. This choice is relevant to study the behaviour of microbiota during the cheese ripening, as evidenced by the different results obtained by other authors in different medium and time conditions.

Conclusion

This study showed that the O₂ or N₂ incubation of LAB in conditions mimicking cheese ripening (a curd-based medium, during 26 days) affects E_h kinetics and the balance of volatile compounds. Whatever the LAB species and the inoculation level, a similar effect on volatile compounds balance was observed. However, the variability between strains into a same or between other species needs to be further studied.

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